

Analytical Examination of Physiological Energy Connections with Improvised Music Therapy, Breathing Exercises and Listening

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Abstract

Changes in social functioning and various aspects of the social process were also found. Increased communication, trust and social contact are just a few examples; others include strengthening resilience and political agency and keeping links. According to Elkkila et al. In Finland, Clark et al. Research conducted by Chong and Yun in Australia and South Korea is an example of music therapy research that is of interest to the reader. A randomized controlled trial was conducted by Erkkila and colleagues to investigate the effectiveness of using music therapy as a strategy for adult patients suffering from depression. The significant effects on depression were remarkable

and when improvised music therapy was paired with breathing exercises and listening assignments. Clark et al conducted a study in Australia and found that a songwriting program is not only possible and acceptable in people with dementia and their caregivers, but also leads to improvements in depressive symptoms and mood, in addition to cognitive performance and social development. To investigate the effects of music therapy on juvenile delinquents, Chong and Yun used a research approach that combined qualitative and quantitative approaches. The resource-oriented approach provided gains in both the participants' self-concepts and their ability to cope with stress and remain resilient. Studies focusing on the elements of music and the strategies used in music therapy are also included here. For example, Scrine criticizes mainstream trauma models. She highlights how music therapy can challenge power relations by supplying the opportunity to reframe perceived risk, foster resistance and build political representation, while encouraging young people to challenge assumptions of safe space and instead move towards practices of structuring safety. In other words, it shows how music therapy can help young people reframe perceived risk, strengthen resistance, and build political agency. This article explores this topic in conjunction with energy, human physiology and psychology.

Keywords: *Improvised Music Therapy, Breathing Exercises, Listening, Physiological Energy, Psychology and Physiology*

1. Introduction

De Witte et al, consisted of analysis of focus group interviews with music therapists dealing with people with moderate mental impairment whose primary emphasis was on stress reduction. Active interventions managed synchronization, release of tension, and immediate relaxation, according to the study's findings. The tempo and dynamics of the music were the most crucial factors to consider when choosing musical interventions to reduce stress. Emphasizing the importance of music for the development of emotional and social skills, growth and well-being, this research collection also includes some fascinating work in ensemble music and music education. These studies prove the usefulness of music for these purposes. According to a study using a variety of research approaches, self-expression, self-confidence, mood, and one's social skills improved because of

participation in a community music program for people with disabilities. There were also notable improvements in communication, as well as increases in social contact and collaborative interaction. Music production has been recognized as an important non-verbal form of self-expression (MacGlone et al.). Holochwost et al. They pay attention to the development and success in their work. This group of researchers concluded that children at risk of poverty and attending orchestral music education programs have a significantly higher growth mindset. There was also evidence of a dose-response relationship for 2-3 years of participation in such programs. Groarke and Hogan found a whole new way to evaluate the eudaimonic functions of music listening and evaluated peak experiences, flow, and transcendence in the context of music listening experiences. Scores were linked to higher levels of both happy and negative emotion; This suggests that listening to eudaimonic music is associated with greater emotional experience, as opposed to a stronger ability to regulate emotions.

2. Weight Loss Response to Energy Balance Interventions

Because of the striking individual variation in weight loss response to energy balance interventions, we need to learn about the mechanism or mechanisms responsible for the active compensatory differences in energy intake, food preferences, and body weight that exist between children and adults. We have extremely limited evidence from energy balance studies conducted after weight loss during the challenging phase of weight maintenance, the time at once after weight loss. How can we decide which subgroups of a population or even individuals will or will not respond to an intervention that includes changes in diet or physical activity?

Measurements of energy intake and output are not correct or correct enough to allow calculation of energy balance over the proper time necessary to understand the processes responsible for excess weight gain. As a result, we need to develop new methods that can accurately measure a person's energy balance while living free for extended periods of time.

3. Activity-Related Energy Expenditure

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Activity-related energy expenditure is the most variable part of daily energy expenditure (DEE), as decided by the activity pattern that includes exercise. Variation in energy expenditure decides when energy intake, energy balance, and ultimately body composition, and when energy imbalance is compensated by the storage or mobilization of body fat. In addition, consistent changes in physical activity through immobilization or exercise training affect body composition through changes in muscle mass. (“Exercise, energy balance and body composition - PMC”) Therefore, elite athletes, such as those taking part in Olympic events, have a lower body fat percentage than the average of similar-aged subjects of the general population. In athletes, body mass index is a better indicator of muscle mass than adiposity . A qualitative interview study conducted by Krause and Davidson discovered that listening to music helps the well-being of older people in residential care in Australia. This was found to be so because listening to music supplied entertainment, pleasure, relaxation, and mood regulation. There is added evidence to suggest that music and music therapy may be beneficial to people currently coping with the effects of cancer. For example, a recent systematic review and meta-analysis conducted by Kohler et al. He discovered that music therapy significantly improved psychological health, quality of life and significantly reduced physical symptom distress in individuals diagnosed with cancer. It was decided that it would be possible and proper to conduct a pilot study using music-based play activities to relieve discomfort in children undergoing hematopoietic stem cell transplantation (SCST) and their caregivers (Holochwost et al.). Hunt et al. likewise focused on cancer treatment; however, they used EEG as part of a case series mixed method design to investigate the neural effects of listening to music over the preferred music in patients experiencing chronic pain from cancer. The analysis showed that common brain responses occur in the theta and low beta range in the right anterior and central gyrus when listening to individualized entrainment-healing music .

noticed sensorimotor changes consistent with the processing of pain during practice-healing music . These changes were not detected during preferred music. Babies and children process music more slowly than adults and use different cortical regions, according to the findings of a comprehensive review by Bower et al., which compiled data from neuroimaging studies on the neural processing of music in children. These two studies are important because they report on the effect of music on the brain and begin to build a picture of how not just music but possibly all forms of art can

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have a huge positive impact on the body. Both studies are important for reporting the effect of music on the brain. As we will see in the next section, this call also includes evaluating the impact that all forms of artistic expression have when combined in many ways.

4. Different Artistic Disciplines and Several Different Art Therapy

Six different studies were conducted to investigate the effects of treatments involving different art forms in clinical settings, with individuals of different ages, and in educational and joint art therapy. In this context, it is important to highlight two randomized controlled trials: Moula et al. In the United Kingdom and Ho et al. in Hong Kong. According to Moula et al. conducted a pilot randomized controlled trial to evaluate the effectiveness of art therapies (music, drama, dance movement, and art therapy) on child and teacher-reported mental and physical outcomes. The results of the experiment were found to be positive.

Exercise-induced fat loss is limited to the largest sustained PAL. The PAL of overweight subjects and obese subjects as assessed by double-label water was like the PAL of normal-weight subjects with an average value of around 1.75 . Activity-induced energy expenditure is similar or slightly higher in most obese subjects. Obese subjects may move less for the same amount of energy due to the increased cost of moving a larger body mass. High body weight leads to high activity-related energy expenditure, even if subjects move less than normal-weight subjects. With exercise training, which results in an added energy expenditure of 2-3 MJ per day, the PAL reaches a maximum value of 2.0-2.4. Therefore, the maximum exercise-induced fat loss is about 0.5 kg per week.

Rodent models are useful for testing hypotheses about the relationship between diet and body weight regulation, as they can be subjected to strict dietary control over extended periods of time and are free of potentially confounding factors such as conscious weight loss. Additionally, the responses of various strains of mice to varying amounts of macronutrients in their diet may supply insight into the regulatory mechanisms at play. However, this great degree of control comes at the expense of questionable applicability to human obesity in terms of translational research. For

example, rodent studies have been crucial in proving the causal role that insulin plays in influencing metabolism, food intake, and fat accumulation (65–71); however, this evidence does not distinguish between CPA and CIM because both models recognize the importance of these processes. On the other hand, the importance of dietary carbohydrates in influencing body weight, as claimed by the CIM, has been shown to be completely unreasonable by other rodent studies.

5. The Evidence in the Fields of the Arts, as well as Continuing to Be Limited to Various Consequences

In any case, further work, research that should ideally involve collaboration in several academic fields, is necessary. For example, Schneider and Rohmann conducted a literature review to explore the impact of school-based arts education on a variety of different skill outcomes. The authors concluded that due to the small sample sizes, few studies, and varied effect sizes, the evidence in the arts as well as for a variety of outcomes stays limited. Holochwost et al. supplies guidance on how the quality of studies can be improved in a complementary conceptual paper. Describe the specific domain of art education activity by "arts education" researchers (e.g., moving instead of painting versus singing), the contexts in which the activity takes place (e.g., by a facilitator as opposed to being taught by a professional artist), and the concept of socio-emotional development targeted in the study.

Witte et al., who conducted the first scoping review on the therapeutic elements of art treatments. It's critical that researchers understand the components of treatments that actually do the job before continuing to run more randomized controlled trials. Therapists have come from a variety of backgrounds, including clinical psychology, clinical social work, clinical social work, dance/movement therapy, art therapy, music therapy, and theater therapy. The findings highlight the key role that the concrete body plays in both the therapeutic process and intersubjective relationships. They also point to the potential impact that somatic and kinetic interventions can have. In addition, as said earlier, they supply useful information and insights into the psychological, physiological and social advantages of participating in the arts. Each contribution not only improves our understanding of what works where and with whom, but also supplies

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methodological roadmaps and recommendations for future research. Collectively, the articles included in this collection illustrate the advantages of working across a continuum of care, including community arts, arts, and health and arts treatments. These advantages are also highlighted by the cross-pollination possibilities offered.

More than twenty studies have been conducted to investigate whether children and adolescents attending regular schools, private schools, or hospitals could receive help from taking part in artistic activities or receiving artistic therapy. The remaining studies focus their attention mostly on adult populations, which can range from the public to members of vulnerable groups or those with medical problems. Parkinson's disease and dementia are two areas that are often reported and that receive considerable attention when associated with older age groups.

Art has the potential to serve as a social glue that brings families, generations, and the wider community together, according to the findings of the many studies included in this call. Douse et al. Ensemble interventions using dance and Engelhard 's intergenerational generations from Shuper and Shuper are two examples that prove dance's ability to bring people together. Research has been conducted on the ability of participatory music to foster expression (MacGlone et al), growth and attainment (Holocwost et al), and well-being (Groarke and Hogan). In addition, participatory music can offer fun, enjoyment and relaxation (Krause and Davidson) for children, adults and seniors alike . According to the findings of Garcia- Arch et al., an intervention program focused on the performing arts may have helped lower levels of implicit bias among members of the public.

There has been an alarming increase in the frequency of this diverse group of diseases in the Western world recently (Kuczmarski et al. 1994). A full third of the population in the United States is now considered obese, and the incidence of youth obesity is rising rapidly, pointing to much more medical damage in the coming decades (Troiano and Flegal 1999).

6. Increase in Use of Energy Storage Devices

Why is there such an increase in the use of energy storage devices? The interaction of genetic, environmental and psychological variables is what determines body weight and composition, as

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well as the amount of energy stored as triglycerides in adipose tissue as a form of energy storage. In the end, these effects have an effect by changing the equation that defines energy balance, which refers to the balance between energy intake and energy expenditure overall. Earlier studies in physiology had led researchers to conclude that the body's weight and energy stores are homeostatically controlled. Whether a person loses or gains weight, harmonious changes occur in energy intake and expenditure. These changes can resist initial disruption. Recent cloning of several obesity-related genes has shed light on the first molecular components of a coherent physiological system to keep energy homeostasis (reviewed in Barsh et al. 2000). Research into the causes of obesity should focus on making sense of the situation within the framework of this physiological system. Acting training was associated with increased levels of empathy in daily life, including emotional, cognitive, and compassionate empathy (Panero and Winner). Numerous studies have focused on the effects of short-term and long-term treatments of the visual arts and art therapy on the development of social and emotional skills in young people (Kastner et al.), as well as expression (Harpazi et al.) and control of emotions in children. (Drake). Savazzi et al. and Tong et al. looked at its effects on clinical and nonclinical adult populations to decide whether art can improve quality of life and general well-being (Pipere et al.). (Hyvonen et al.; Erkkila et al.) We have large multicenter, randomized controlled trials that convincingly argue, through robust designs, that dance movement and music therapy are an important force for reducing depression.

These trials were conducted by several different centers around the world. Evidence is presented for the contribution of psychodrama to reducing trauma symptoms (Yanai and Ron; Giacomucci and Marquit), in addition to substantial evidence for the effectiveness of art therapies in reducing symptoms of illness. It has been reported that a similar effect in reducing anxiety and depression occurs in art therapy (Havsteen -Franklin et al.). In addition, evidence is presented for the contribution of art therapy to reducing trauma symptoms. More randomized controlled trials examining the efficacy of art with different populations are needed, as well as experimental studies targeting fewer specific measurable components enriched by a deep understanding of subjective experiences to move forward. our direct understanding of cause and effect and generates strong empirical evidence. To do this, more randomized controlled trials examining the efficacy of art in different populations are necessary. We believe that if sufficient financial support is given, art and

art therapy can be applied both more effectively and more accurately. Art therapy publications (Zubala et al; Shamri Zeevi ; Kaimal et al.) respond not only to the needs created by the pandemic, but also to the longer-term and evolving artistic digital language spoken by the diverse populations we serve. These publications report current developments in the use of digital technologies. As digital technologies continue to advance in sophistication, it is predicted that research into other artistic applications will advance by supporting embodied 3D real-time artistic experiences with significant psychological, physiological and/or social value. This is something to be expected.

7. The Effect of Music on the Brain

Bower et al. and Hunt et al. On the effect of music on the brain, Moula et al. The impact of art therapies on children's sleep quality and studies emphasizing the physiological and neurological benefits of engaging in visual arts and art therapy for Alzheimer's patients are some examples of studies that highlight the impact of art and art therapies on health. neurophysiology, motor skills, physical health and other biomarkers (Savazzi et al.). Wearable devices, electroencephalograms , functional magnetic resonance imaging scans, and other similar devices are gaining popularity as tools for trying to capture how our physiology is directly affected by not only passively seeing but also actively participating . It should come as no surprise that members of the neuroscience community take an interest in the arts. However, expensive equipment also requires corresponding financial expenses. Comparable amounts of money are needed for large randomized controlled trials involving several centers. Art studies have historically been underfunded; A comparably large level of financial investment is needed to conduct extensive and expensive research that could fully unravel why art is so effective for our mental health. Currently, de Witte et al. art treatments can also be right for a variety of various applications of art. These factors were included in systematic reviews of art therapies. For example, art is likely to promote full immersion in art-making processes (also known as "editing"), embodying things that may be difficult to articulate or grasp (also known as "embodiment").) and clarifying experience (through "symbolism and metaphors") while preserving complexity and possibility at the same time can be the answer to many of our struggles and challenges.

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While genes have been found to play a role in the regulation of body fat, it is safe to assume that the increasing prevalence of obesity is not due to a recent change in the genetics of the Western world. This is because the role of genes in body fat regulation has now been set up. The obesity trend must have been with us for a long time; however, it has only recently appeared on a large scale because of changes in the environment, particularly the availability and composition of food and the reduced need for physical exertion. It is highly likely that over thousands of years of human evolution, the ability to store fat during times of abundant nutrition was a positive trait chosen by natural selection. The "thrifty gene" theory is the term given to the concept that humans have evolved to effectively store excess energy as fat to cope with periodic hunger. This idea has been given a name (Neel 1999). A nearly 250-pound obese person has the ability to conserve energy stores for about 150 days of total fasting! This impressive energy reserve is the result of two factors: the high energy content of triglycerides compared to polysaccharides and the almost completely anhydrous storage of triglycerides. On the other hand, polysaccharides such as glycogen are hydrated in their storage form , reducing the efficiency at which they can be used as fuel.

8. Energy Balance Idea

To have a proper understanding of obesity, it is necessary to first grasp the idea of energy balance. Assuming a person has no problems with nutrient absorption, then the only way a person's stored energy can increase is if their energy intake is greater than their whole-body energy expenditure. Energy expenditure can occur in three diverse ways: through physical activity, through basal metabolism, and through adaptive thermogenesis . The term "physical activity" refers to any voluntary movement, while the term "basal metabolism" refers to the many biochemical processes necessary to sustain life. The process of losing energy in the form of heat in response to changes in the environment, such as when an organism is exposed to cold or its diet changes, is called adaptive thermogenesis . It is important to note that the line separating what is known as "basal metabolism" from "adaptive thermogenesis" cannot always be drawn with absolute precision. Often, mammals refer to environments with temperatures below their body temperature, and

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sometimes even much lower, as home. It is therefore possible that the estimate of the amount of energy used in response to cold is rather arbitrary compared to the amount of energy considered to be part of basal metabolism. While research is conducted on the processes responsible for the change brought about by art, studies on the results of participation in the arts are also conducted. This comprehensive collection of research on art and the benefits of art treatments is outstanding, the results are encouraging and the potential avenues for future work are remarkably interesting. The variety of art and art therapies benefits covered in studies is also surprising.

is both a historical and a modern development for researchers who, following the logic of IM Sechenov , try to reduce the processes of functioning and development of the mind to the underlying physiological mechanisms. (in the broadest sense). LS Vygotsky, along with others, offered a contrasting perspective; This way of thinking was revolutionary. Vygotsky supplied a concise description of cultural, psychological, and physiological phenomena in his diaries of the 1920s and 1930s. His analyzes ranged from physiological psychology to psychological physiology. This study of the interplay between cultural, psychological, and physiological reality can be represented in various forms in the work of NE Vvedensky , AA Ukhtomsky and NA Bernshtein , EN Sokolov , PK Anohin , AR Luria , and IM Feigenberg , among others. . The following concepts are used as non-classical and non-classical paradigms in the scientific process of the XXI century:

The problem of forming the body was solved by NA Bernstein, the neuronal stimulus model was developed by EN Sokolov , functional system concepts were developed by PK Anohin , systematic localization of mental functions was developed by AR Luria , and probabilistic prediction of brain activity was developed by IM Feigenberg .

Through the lens of non-classical and non-classical principles of rationality, the author of this article tries to define the problematic topic of psychological physiology (MK). Mamardashvili , VS Stepin, MS Guseltseva). The authors used non-classical psychological physiology to argue for the assumption that culture and the laws of development of the mind are irreducible to the physiological mechanisms of their application. They also argued for the methodological failure of attempts to solve the Cartesian psychophysiological problem by using various correlation

techniques (even the most complex ones) to bridge the gap between the brain, mind, and culture. This was done while examining issues related to the relationship between the brain, mind, and culture. The expansion of contemporary scientific knowledge is defined by a comprehensive revision of the conceptual framework. In addition to "classical" and "non-classical" methods for solving fundamental and applied problems, there is also a "non-classical" research paradigm that is being actively developed (Mezzich , Zinchenko , Krasnov , Pervichko , Kulygina , 2013; Pervichko , Zinchenko , 2014; Zinchenko , Pervichko , 2012 a, b; Zinchenko , Pervichko , 2013).

The adoption of a post-neoclassical technique in scientific enterprise is followed by a reassessment of not only the general scientific method, but also a particular scientific approach. The latter is showed by the updating of the ontological model of the object of study and, as a direct consequence, the creation of new experimental technologies and new lines of research based on these technologies. Both contemporary neuroscience and psychophysiology are still part of the conceptual reshaping process.

non -invasive imaging techniques in brain activity (such as functional magnetic resonance imaging, fMRI and positron emission tomography, PET) allowed scientists to understand cognitive processes (perception, thinking, and consciousness), as well as social cognition and social behavior. Therefore, the last decade has resulted in the rapid emergence of new interdisciplinary research areas at the intersection of neuroscience and social science (especially social psychology and behavioral economics). ("From physiological psychology to psychological physiology ...") These new research areas are termed "social neuroscience" and "social psychophysiology", respectively (Lieberman , 2007; Adolphs , 2009, 2010; Amodio , 2010).

thermoneutral state eight to twelve hours after the last meal . It should come as no surprise that the metabolic rates of mammals vary on a continuous scale depending on the environmental variables to which the organism is exposed.

9. Specific Cellular Events

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In general, certain cellular events can induce or prevent obesity only if they change one's total energy equation. This means that obesity can be caused or prevented by cellular events. For example, if there was no such thing as the idea of energy balance, it would be thought that obesity and its accompanying problems could be alleviated by directly reducing the formation of adipose tissue. This is not the case, as has been shown in several experimental models in which the differentiation, development, and survival of fat cells are deliberately inhibited. Rather than producing healthy and lean mice, the experiment appears to have caused the animals to suffer from a lack of sufficient stores to store extra energy, as well as the loss of important hormones produced by adipocytes (Ross et al 1993, Moitra et al 1998, Shimomura et al 1998) . Increased blood lipid levels, fatty deposits in the liver, diabetes and ultimately death are the consequences. In contrast, the finding that a genetically modified animal has a lower body fat percentage does not show that the targeted gene per se plays a role in fat formation. Instead, an error occurs in some components of the overall energy balancing system, most often for food taken or the amount of energy spent. Known as "conceptual cohesion," the method managed setting up new scientific societies and laboratories, as well as educational programs and academic journals. Since 2006, the fields of "Social Cognitive and Affective Neuroscience" (SCAN) and "Social Neuroscience" have each seen the publication of their own special editions. In addition, there is a scientific organization known as the "Social Neuroscience Society" and several key monographs and tutorials have been produced (Blascovich , 2000; Blascovich , Mendes, 2010). The scientific paradigm has changed, resulting in significant changes in the field of psychophysiology. These changes transformed the field from "classical" (Wundtian) psychophysiology to the contemporary science of the neural mechanisms underlying mental processes and states. In contemporary psychophysiology, emphasis is placed not only on neurons and neural networks (macro-objects), but also on different organelles, molecular and genetic processes found in brain cells. In 2006 Professor Richard Magin coined the word " nanoneuronics " to describe the unprecedented level of work being done in contemporary psychophysiology (Akay, 2006).

The current science of psychophysiology is expanding both in terms of the "breadth" of its knowledge (ontology) and the "depth" (different fields of psychology) of its knowledge (neurons). New areas of expertise are currently being created. These new competencies include important

places for closely related fields of creative research such as "cognitive psychophysiology" and "social psychophysiology", both of which have important places. Many people think that a person's living conditions, and upbringing contribute to the formation of his personality. However, environment and culture are not the only factors that have an impact. The evolutionary process manages social behavior that has a genetic basis formed by (natural) selection and has its origins in the instinctive actions of animals. The importance of investigating the biological basis of social behavior, which is not always visible under layers of culture, has not diminished; It is a task for researchers representing a wide range of scientific fields, including ethology, animal psychology, psychogenetics, evolutionary biology, evolutionary psychology, ethnography, and sociobiology, among others (Asmolov et al., 2013, 2014; Dawkins, 2014; Wilson, 2015; Wilson, 1976). Within the scope of social neurosciences and social psychophysiology, the neural structures of the brain related to social behavior and intercultural communication service are investigated (Lorenz, 1998; Palmer, Palmer, 2003; Asmolov et al., 2013, 2014; Schechter, Chernorizov 2011; Falikman, Cole, 2014; Martin, Wiggs, Weisberg, 1997; Blascovich, 2000; Blascovich et al., 2010; Wangbing et al., 2011). In particular, the following brain mechanisms have been explored: social cognition (also known as social, emotional, and cultural intelligence); verbal and nonverbal (emotions, gestures) communication, including intercultural communication studies; ritualized behavior; aggression and altruism; Social hierarchy; keeping "individual distance" in communication; dysfunction of social dialogue (social phobia, schizophrenia, autism).

complex investigations that fit perfectly in the spirit of contemporary psychophysiology, which relates to a combination of various scientific fields centered around a common core called "a vector of cognition" (Man's cognition). Psychophysiological research of the biological basis of human social behavior is based on the analysis of the evolution of social relations in communities of living organisms according to the following scheme. Systems of inanimate nature (living systems of the community and anonymous communities), family groups and sexual dimorphism (personified communities), and communities of individuals with various levels of sexual dimorphism (Schechter, Chernorizov 2011; Asmolov et al., 2013, 2014).

This approach enables various aspects of biologically based social behavior research to be combined into a single evolutionary developmental scheme. Additionally, it emphasizes areas

considered to be within the field of social psychophysiology (competence). Some features of human social behavior can be explained by principles that underpin brain function, which can also serve as a model for structuring social connections in society (Bekhtereva , 1994).

10. Conclusion

Studies of the psychophysiology of brain activity in relation to social interaction processes have been recreated using various virtual reality contexts. Studies on specific features of brain activity in a virtual reality (VR) environment, patterns of ethno-cultural identity processes and the formation of interethnic and interfaith attitudes, the behavior of "(virtual) avatars" and the development of communication skills with partners belonging to diverse cultures or ethnic groups, the development of social psychophysiology. are some of the most popular areas? These studies explore important aspects of the security issue in the modern world, including terrorism (Zinchenko , Shaigerova , Shilko , 2011; Chaiguerova , Soldatova , 2013; Soldatova , Shaigerova , Shlyapnikov , 2008) (Zinchenko , 2011; Zinchenko , Zotova , 2014), extreme situations (Soldatova , Zinchenko , Shaigerova , 2011), extremism (Zinchenko , 2014), social instability ((Soldatova , Shaigerova , 2002, 2015). The combination of virtual reality (VR) systems with online brain activity recording has opened. While people are immersed in VR Increases the chance of objectively assessing the strength of the "immersion effect". This effect is also known as the "presence effect." Electroencephalography (EEG), magnetoencephalography (MEG), positron emission tomography (PET), and functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) are some examples of modern non-invasive imaging techniques that can be used to examine (Wiederhold , Rizzo , 2005; Baumgartner et al., 2008 The study of the effect of macronutrient composition, such as protein, carbohydrate, and fat balance, on long-term body weight is still in its infancy, and gene-diet interactions in the nutritional response to diets of varying composition are only just beginning to emerge. Particularly, in collectivist countries traditionally thought of as Eastern cultures, the feeling of close relatives or friends has been shown to stimulate parts of the brain related to one's own self-concept. This discovery is something that can be seen because of including "dear and close people" (friends and family) in one's self-concept. This effect does not occur in civilizations

with a strong emphasis on individualism (traditionally Western cultures). The discovery that differences in cultural norms are reflected in different patterns of brain activity has supplied conclusive evidence for the critical necessity of added research and development of psychophysiological methods for their application in cross-cultural and cross-cultural research .

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